

Exploring the temperature dependence of magnetic properties and magnetoimpedance effect in Co-rich microwires

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ABSTRACT

We studied the temperature dependence of the magnetic properties and giant magnetoimpedance, GMI, effect in as-prepared and annealed $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{1.2}\text{Si}_{1.5}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with nearly-zero magnetostriction. Substantial changes in the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, value and magnetic field, H , dependence, and in the hysteresis loops upon heating were observed. The modification in the hysteresis loop shape upon heating correlates with a change in the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies. In as-prepared and most of the heat treated samples the hysteresis loop transformation from inclined to squared upon heating correlates with the change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies from double-peak to single-peak. However, the stress-annealed at 118 MPa samples present better thermal stability of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies and hysteresis loops. In all the studied samples an increase in the GMI ratio at 300 °C was observed. The origin of the observed temperature dependences is discussed in terms of the Hopkinson effect, temperature dependence and relaxation of internal stresses, induced magnetic anisotropy, and temperature dependence of the magnetostriction coefficient.

1. Introduction

Amorphous magnetic materials have attracted attention for several decades due to their unique combination of outstanding magnetic softness and exceptional mechanical properties, as well as the fast and inexpensive fabrication technique [1,2]. The excellent soft magnetic properties of amorphous materials are commonly attributed to the absence of any crystalline structure defects (dislocations, twins, grain boundaries, etc.) which are the main factors limiting the magnetic softness of the crystalline materials [2,3]. Such combination of physical properties has led to the development of promising applications involving amorphous materials in various industrial sectors, such as electrical engineering, microelectronics, sensing, medicine, aviation, home entertainment, electronic surveillance, etc. [4–7].

Excellent magnetic softness and unusual magnetic properties such as magnetic bistability or the highest giant magnetoimpedance (GMI) effect have been observed in amorphous wires [8–11]. It is worth mentioning, that the magnetic bistability and GMI effect can also be observed in amorphous ribbons [12,13]. However, the cylindrical symmetry of the amorphous wires is more appropriate for the implementation of the spontaneous magnetic bistability and the high GMI effect [8–11,13,14].

The origin of the GMI effect is commonly attributed to a change in the skin depth, δ , of a magnetically soft conductor upon an applied magnetic field, H [8,10]. The skin depth of the AC current, δ , is related with the magnetic softness of the magnetic wires through the circumferential magnetic permeability, μ_{ϕ} , as provided elsewhere [8,10,13]:

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$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi \sigma \mu_{\phi} f}} \quad (1)$$

being σ - the electrical conductivity and f - the frequency of the AC current flowing through the wire. High circumferential magnetic permeability, μ_{ϕ} , is commonly observed in Co-rich amorphous wires with nearly-zero magnetostriction coefficient [8,10,13–15].

Accordingly, amorphous wires prepared using various rapid melt quenching techniques have been intensively studied since the '70s [8–16]. Thus, several technological applications of amorphous wires have been developed [6,7,9,16]. For most of emerging applications of amorphous materials the reduced dimensionality, biocompatibility or improved corrosion resistance are demanded. Consequently, considerable attention is paid to the development of micro-nanoscaled amorphous materials using melt quenching [6–8]. One of such techniques, suitable for the preparation of amorphous wires with micrometric-nanometric diameters coated by insulating and flexible glass is the so-called Taylor-Ulitovsky method [7,13,17–19]. This technique allows the preparation of microwires with rather extended range of diameters (from 0.5 to 100 μm), coated with flexible, thin, insulating, and biocompatible glass [17–21]. The fabrication and primary magnetic characterization of such microwires are reported since the '70s [22,23]. Extensive studies of soft magnetic properties, the GMI effect, magnetic bistability and the related single domain wall propagation are realized since the '90s [13,17,24–26].

Excellent soft magnetic properties and high GMI effect together with superior mechanical and anticorrosive properties of glass-coated microwires allowed to develop diverse applications, such as magnetic sensors or tunable microwave composite materials [17,27–30].

One of such emerging applications of the glass-coated microwires is the wireless sensing technique allowing monitoring of external stimuli (magnetic field, temperature, stress) by designing of the composites with glass-coated microwires inclusions [17,27–30]. The proposed method is based on the theoretically predicted [31] and later experimentally confirmed [27,29,30,32,33] dependence of the effective permittivity, ε_{ef} , of such composites containing the magnetic wire inclusions on the magnetic wires impedance. On the other hand, magnetic wires impedance is substantially affected by external stimulus, such as magnetic field or applied stress, giving rise to GMI or stress-impedance effects [8,10,13,16,17]. Accordingly, such composites with magnetic wire inclusions have been proposed for external stimuli monitoring [27,29,30,32,33]. The key elements of such smart composites are the ferromagnetic wires with GMI effect sensitive to external stimuli (magnetic field, stress or temperature) [17].

On the other hand, for magnetic field sensor applications, temperature stability of the GMI effect is critical. Studies of the dependence of the GMI effect on temperature are essential for assessing the feasibility of such applications. However, there are very few reports on temperature dependence of the GMI effect and most of these studies were carried out in different amorphous materials (ribbons or thick magnetic wires without glass-coating) [34–36]. Additionally, the temperature dependence of the GMI effect has been studied in rather limited temperature range [35,36]. Recently, a substantial influence of heating on GMI effect is observed for Fe-rich amorphous microwires [37].

However, the highest GMI effect and better magnetic softness are commonly reported in Co-rich amorphous microwires with vanishing magnetostriction coefficient [8,10,17,28]. Magnetic properties and GMI effect are studied in details at room temperature. However, recently was observed a substantial magnetic hardening and deterioration of the GMI effect in Co-rich microwires after heat treatment. After detailed studies, was reported that such deterioration of the magnetic softness can be prevented by either Joule heating or stress-annealing [17,38]. Transverse magnetic anisotropy was observed after stress annealing of Co-rich microwires. Such stress-annealing induced anisotropy is affected not only by the annealing temperature, but also by the stresses applied during annealing [38]. Particularly, was shown that stress-annealed

samples can present better GMI effect and lower magnetic anisotropy field, H_k . Better GMI performance was also observed in the Co-rich after Joule heating [17]. Accordingly, we can expect that the temperature dependence of as-prepared, Joule heated and stress-annealed Co-rich microwires can be substantially different.

The purpose of this paper is to provide our last experimental results on the temperature dependence of the GMI effect and hysteresis loops for as-prepared and postprocessed Co-rich microwires.

2. Experimental

We studied the temperature influence on the magnetic properties and the GMI effect in amorphous $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires, previously studied at room temperature [38]. Such $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwire with metallic nucleus diameter $d = 22.8 \mu\text{m}$ and total diameter $D = 23.2 \mu\text{m}$ has been prepared by modified Taylor-Ulitovsky fabrication technique. The fabrication method essentially consists of melting a metal alloy inside a Duran-type glass tube by a high-frequency inductor (see Fig. 1). After forming a capillary from a softened glass tube, the molten metallic alloy fills the glass capillary by wetting. Then, the metallic alloy inside the softened glass capillary is drawn out, cooled by a stream of coolant (water) and wound onto a rotating spool [17]. The amorphous structure of the studied microwire is confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) (see Fig. 2). A wide halo is observed in the XRD spectra of both as-prepared and annealed at 370 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig. 1. Image of the experimental facility for fabrication of microwires.

Fig. 2. XRD of as-prepared and annealed at 370 °C for 3h sample (a) and DSC curve of the as-prepared microwire (b).

(3h) samples (Fig. 2a). Crystallization of the studied sample is observed at about 560 °C using DSC (heating rate -10 K/min). The magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , (-0.3×10^{-6}) was evaluated using the small angle magnetization rotation (SAMR) method [38].

Similarly to the case of Fe-rich microwires [37], the hysteresis loops of studied samples were measured using the vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) MicroSense EV9 and the fluxmetric method [37,39].

The latter (fluxmetric) method allows measuring the hysteresis loops of a 10 cm long microwire placed inside a long and thin magnetizing coil, and the magnetization is measured by a 2 cm long pick-up coil [40]. Generally, this method allows us to measure the hysteresis loops of soft magnetic microwires at room temperature with high precision, since we can obtain about 2500 experimental points at a magnetic field amplitude of about 400 A/m or even smaller.

However, this technique is not suitable for measurements at different temperatures. Therefore, for the evaluation of the temperature dependence of hysteresis loops we used the VSM magnetometry, suitable for measurements of the hysteresis loops of 5 mm long samples from room temperature up to 300 °C, as previously described in detail [37,39].

The hysteresis loops are presented as the dependence of the normalized magnetization, M/M_0 on the magnetic field, H , being M - the magnetic moment at a given magnetic field and temperature and M_0 - the magnetic moment of studied microwire measured at ambient temperature and maximum magnetic field amplitude, H_m .

The GMI effect is expressed through the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, determined as [10,13]:

$$\Delta Z / Z = [Z(H) - Z(H_{max})] / Z(H_{max}), \quad (2)$$

where Z is the microwire impedance, H and H_{max} , the applied DC magnetic field and the maximum field, respectively.

Specially designed experimental facility allowed impedance measurements of the sample and evaluation of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies in a temperature, T , ranging from room temperature up to 300 °C at frequencies, f , up to 110 MHz [39].

All the studies have been carried out in as-prepared and post-processed samples. As reported earlier, stress-annealing allows to modify the magnetic anisotropy and substantially improve the GMI effect of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ amorphous microwires [38,40]. While, unusual magnetic hardening and, in most of the cases, a decrease in the GMI effect is reported after conventional annealing of Co-rich microwires [38]. The alternative technique allowing to avoid magnetic hardening and to improve the GMI effect is Joule heating [41]. Therefore, we investigated the heating influence on the magnetic properties and the GMI effect of as-prepared, stress-annealed and Joule heated $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires.

When we selected the annealing conditions (temperature of stress-annealing and DC current value for Joule heating), we have considered the crystallization temperature (about 560 °C, see Fig. 2) as well as previous knowledge on Joule heating of amorphous materials. Thus, previously was demonstrated that the Joule heating performed at current density, j , of 30–45 A/mm² produces a heating up to 400 °C [42, 43]. Theoretically, similar temperatures were obtained for the glass-coated microwires ($d = 18$ μm) annealed at $I \approx 30$ mA [44]. In addition, it has been experimentally demonstrated (by magnetic hardening and by drop in the electrical resistivity) and then confirmed through a rigorous assessment, taking into account convection and radiative heat transfer, that Joule heating at $j > 200$ A/mm² produces crystallization of the glass-coated microwires [42,45,46]. The used I -value (32 mA) corresponds to $j \approx 78$ A/mm²: such j -values are clearly below $j \approx 200$ A/mm², which can produce the crystallization [42/46]. On the other hand, the Joule heating carried out at $j \approx 78$ A/mm², allowed to substantially improve the GMI effect [41].

3. Results and discussion

Low-field hysteresis loop of as-prepared and annealed at different conditions $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires measured at room temperature are shown in Fig. 3. As can be observed from Fig. 3, as-prepared and Joule heated microwire presents excellent magnetic softness with coercivity, H_c , of about 5 A/m and magnetic anisotropy field, H_k , of about 200 A/m (see Fig. 3a–d). Similarly to that reported previously, higher remanent magnetization with more rectangular hysteresis loop shape is observed in both stress-annealed samples (see Fig. 3b and c). In both cases, the H_c -values were 35 and 15 A/m for the samples stress-annealed at 300 °C with applied tensile stress, σ , of 118 MPa and 472 MPa, respectively.

Accordingly, the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at room temperature of all studied samples also differ substantially. As shown in Fig. 4, double -peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed in as-prepared and Joule heated samples over the whole frequency range. For the microwire stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa (with almost rectangular hysteresis loop, as shown in Fig. 3b), instead a single -peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is observed in the whole frequency range (see Fig. 4b). The $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence for the microwire stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 472$ MPa is different: a single -peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is observed up to $f \leq 20$ MHz, while for $f \geq 30$ MHz double -peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed (see Fig. 4c).

Such variation of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies correlates satisfactorily with the modification of the hysteresis loops. The $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence

Fig. 3. Hysteresis loops of studied as-prepared (a), stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$ (b) and $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ (c) and Joule heated at 32 mA for 3 min (d) microwires.

and the $\Delta Z/Z$ -value are linked with the type of magnetic anisotropy [13, 47]. Thus, the double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are commonly attributed to circumferential magnetic anisotropy of the magnetic wires [47]. While, the single-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies with the decay from $H = 0$ are predicted and experimentally observed for magnetic wires with axial magnetic anisotropy [10,13,47].

Additionally, the H_m -values corresponding to the maximum $\Delta Z/Z$ -values on $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are attributed to the average magnetic anisotropy field values, H_k [10,13,47]. Accordingly, the modification of the hysteresis loops upon postprocessing correlates with the observed $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies.

Substantial changes in the hysteresis loops (see Fig. 5) and the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed upon heating. The general tendency is that upon annealing the hysteresis loops become more squared. This behavior is observed in all the samples with exception of the sample stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$ (Fig. 5b) (in which even at room temperature the hysteresis loop is almost rectangular). In all the samples the hysteresis loops measured at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were almost perfectly rectangular. Observed modification of the hysteresis loops correlates with the influence of the annealing on the hysteresis loops of Co-rich microwires: a transformation of linear hysteresis loop into rectangular one upon furnace annealing of Co-rich microwires of different compositions, as reported elsewhere [38,48]. A decrease in M/M_0 (observed in all studied samples) must be related to approaching the Curie temperature, T_c .

We paid main attention to the low magnetic field region, since the coercivity and the magnetic anisotropy field of the studied samples are quite low (5 A/m and 100 A/m, respectively). However, at $H \leq 1\text{ kA/m}$ the hysteresis loops diverge. As can be observed from the hysteresis loops measured up to 15 kA/m (see Fig. 5a inset), such divergence

disappears at high enough magnetic field. The origin of the observed behavior can be explained considering the contribution of the closure domains arising at the ends of the magnetic wires. The existence of such closure domains has been proved experimentally (by measuring of the magnetization profile using a short movable pick-up coil) and theoretically [49]. We assume that for the 10 cm long samples this contribution is negligible, however for the case of 20 times shorter samples (0.5 cm) this contribution becomes relevant.

Consequently, substantial modification of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating is also observed. Effect of heating up to $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of all studied samples is depicted in Figs. 6–9: for as-prepared (Fig. 6), stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$ (Fig. 7) and for $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ (Fig. 8) and for Joule heated microwire (Fig. 9).

From Fig. 6 we can deduce that in the as-prepared sample, both the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies shape and the maximum $\Delta Z/Z$ -value, $\Delta Z/Z_m$, change upon heating. Thus, the double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence transforms into single-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence at $T > 150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In this sample, single-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed for all the temperatures.

However, rather different $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed for the samples stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$ (see Fig. 7). Instead, double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed for the samples stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ up to $T = 200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (see Fig. 8). While a transformation from double peak to single-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is observed at $T > 200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

From the experimental data provided in Figs. 6–9 we can deduce that the unique sample in which $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ maintains its (single peak) dependence in the whole range of studied temperatures is the microwire stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$, i.e., the microwire

Fig. 4. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared (a), stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa (b) and $\sigma = 472$ MPa (c) and Joule heated at 32 mA for 3 min (d) $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ microwires.

with weak stress-annealing induced magnetic anisotropy with almost rectangular hysteresis loops. However, as can be observed from Figs. 6–9, in this sample stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa $H_m = 0$ in the whole T range, as can be observed in Fig. 10. In this sample, $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are rather stable for $50 \leq T \leq 250$ °C, being about 230% (Fig. 10a). Even more stable $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values for the whole T range are observed for the sample stress-annealed at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 472$ MPa; however, in this sample a change from double-peak to single peak dependence is observed at $T = 300$ °C ($H_m \sim 0$ at $T = 300$ °C, see Fig. 10b). The strongest changes in the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed in as-prepared and Joule heated samples: as observed from Fig. 10b—a change from double-peak to single peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are observed at $T = 200$ °C in both as-prepared and Joule heated samples. This change in the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies correlates with a minimum in $H_m(T)$ dependencies. One more common feature of the $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ dependencies observed in all samples is an increase observed at $T = 300$ °C (see Fig. 10a).

The highest $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -values are observed in the microwire subjected to Joule heating (see Fig. 10a). A transformation of linear hysteresis loop into rectangular has been previously observed in Co-rich microwires upon annealing [38,40,48]. The origin of such hysteresis loops transformation from linear to rectangular is explained by the change in the magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , value and sign [38]. Additionally, the relaxation of internal stresses should lead to a change in the domain structure related with an increase in the volume of the inner axially magnetized core and, hence, with a

modification of the hysteresis loop [17].

To explain the unusual temperature dependence of the GMI effect observed in the Co-rich microwires we must consider several factors. As experimentally shown elsewhere, the magnetoresistance effect of amorphous materials is quite low [50]. On the other hand, the electrical resistance of amorphous materials is almost temperature independent in the temperature range between room temperature and crystallization temperature (usually above 500 °C) [50–52]. Therefore, the origin of the temperature dependence of the GMI effect should be related with the $\delta(T)$ dependence. Given that δ is affected by μ_ϕ through eq. (1), we must pay attention of temperature dependence of μ_ϕ .

The observed change in the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies correlates with the modification in the hysteresis loops upon heating and reflects a change in the magnetic anisotropy of the studied microwires. As previously discussed, the shape of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies is linked to the magnetic anisotropy of the magnetic wires [10,47]. The double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are predicted and experimentally observed elsewhere for amorphous microwires with circumferential magnetic anisotropy in the outer shell [10,47]. The field of maximum, H_m , on $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies is associated with the magnetic anisotropy field at MHz frequencies [10,47]. Therefore, observed change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating correlates with the effect of heating on the hysteresis loops provided in Fig. 4: change from weak transverse magnetic anisotropy to axial magnetic anisotropy.

As mentioned above, an increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ is observed in all the microwires at $T = 300$ °C. The decrease in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ observed in as-prepared and Joule heated samples must be associated with lower magnetic permeability of the microwires with squared hysteresis loops. Similar decrease in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ upon annealing has been previously reported and explained by the transformation of the linear hysteresis loop of Co-rich microwires into rectangular upon annealing [38].

Fig. 5. Effect of heating on hysteresis loops of as-prepared (a), stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ °C}$ for $\sigma = 118\text{ MPa}$ (b) and $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ (c) and Joule heated (d) microwires.

Similarly to that discussed previously for Fe-rich microwires [37], the increase in $\Delta Z/Z_m$ at $T \approx 300\text{ °C}$ can be attributed to the Hopkinson effect. The Hopkinson effect origin is commonly explained by a faster decrease in the constant of magnetic anisotropy with the temperature compared to the decrease in the magnetization [53,54]. Accordingly, a magnetic permeability maximum can be observed at temperatures slightly below the Curie temperature, T_c . From our previous experimental studies we must assume that T_c of the studied sample is about 325 °C [38]. Therefore, such interpretation looks reasonable.

However, evidently the internal stresses relaxation upon heating is another relevant factor that affects the magnetoelastic anisotropy and hence the GMI effect of the studied microwires. As discussed elsewhere [10,38,47], circumferential magnetic anisotropy in Co-rich wires with vanishing magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , is explained considering the features of the internal stresses induced during the fabrication process of the amorphous wires. For glass-coated microwires, the largest component of the internal stress tensor is axial within the larger part of the metal nucleus [17–19]. Therefore, change in the magnetostriction coefficient sign upon heating or even change in the internal stresses (with mostly axial orientation) must affect the magnetic anisotropy and hence the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the studied Co-rich microwire. Correspondingly, the possible origins of the observed temperature dependences are either the Hopkinson effect, the change of the internal stresses and the temperature dependence of the magnetostriction coefficient.

It is worth noting, that the GMI effect and the hysteresis loops of the microwire subjected to stress-annealing at $T_{ann} = 300\text{ °C}$ for $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ show the highest thermal stability: as can be deduced from Fig. 10,

the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -magnitude is almost constant within the whole range of studied temperature. Additionally, the double-peak shape $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of this microwires are maintained up to 250 °C and the values change rather slightly up to $T = 200\text{ °C}$. Such behavior correlates with earlier reported partial irreversibility of the stress-annealing magnetic anisotropy in amorphous microwires [55]. Accordingly, both stress-annealed samples can be suitable for using in magnetic sensors applications in extended temperature range. In the other two samples the irreversible changes in both samples in both $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies and $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value are produced after heating above $T = 100\text{ °C}$.

An example of such change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies and $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value after heating is provided in Fig. 11, where $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the samples subjected to Joule heating measured at room temperature before heating and after heating up to 100 and 150 °C are provided. In these samples the highest $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -value is observed at room temperature (see Fig. 4). As can be appreciated from Fig. 11, after heating to 100 °C still the double-peak $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence is observed at room temperature. However, after heating to 150 °C and subsequent cooling back to room temperature $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependence measured in room temperature substantially changes: it transforms into single-peak (see Fig. 11).

As discussed earlier [56,57], the irreversible character of the stress-annealing induced magnetic anisotropy of the amorphous materials can be attributed not only to the redistribution of the internal stresses due to back-stresses, but also to topological short-range ordering (also called as structural anisotropy). The origin of such induced magnetic anisotropy is commonly attributed to the angular distribution of the atomic bonds and small anisotropic structural rearrangements at temperatures close to the glass transition temperature [56,57].

Fig. 6. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared microwire measured at 100 °C (a), at 150 °C (b), 200 °C (c) and 300 °C (d).

Fig. 7. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa sample measured at 100 °C (a), at 150 °C (b), 200 °C (c) and 300 °C (d).

Fig. 8. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{ann} = 300^\circ\text{C}$ for $\sigma = 472\text{ MPa}$ sample measured at 100°C (a), at 150°C (b), 200°C (c) and 300°C (d).

Fig. 9. Modification of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies upon heating of the Joule heated samples measured at different T .

Fig. 10. $\Delta Z/Z_m(T)$ (a) and $H_m(T)$ (b) dependencies evaluated from $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies.

Fig. 11. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of the samples subjected to Joule heated measured at $f = 100$ MHz at room temperature before heating and after heating up to 100 and 150 °C.

Accordingly, stress-annealed microwires can be more indicated for the development of magnetic sensors working at extended temperature range, while the higher sensitivity of the GMI effect upon heating is observed in as-prepared or Joule heated microwires.

As can be observed from Figs. 4, 6–9, GMI hysteresis is observed in the low-field $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies for all the studied samples. In Fig. 12 we plotted the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies at low magnetic field for as-prepared and stress-annealed ($T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa) samples measured at ambient temperature and at 300 °C (see Fig. 12). The origin of the GMI hysteresis in magnetic wires has been previously discussed in terms of the magnetostatic interaction of the inner axially magnetized core with the outer domain shell, the irreversible switches of the transverse permeability related with the domain wall structure transitions and considering helical magnetic anisotropy in the outer domain shell [58–60]. The influence of the magnetostatic interaction between the inner axially magnetized core with the outer domain shell can be evidenced in the low field region of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies. As can be noticed from Fig. 12, the observed GMI hysteresis is frequency independent. Therefore, the observed GMI hysteresis can most likely be attributed to the magnetostatic interaction of inner axially magnetized core and the outer domain shell [58]. It is worth mentioning, that the magnetostatic interaction between the inner axially magnetized core and outer domain shell is affected by several parameters, such as the inner axially magnetized core volume of coercivity. These parameters

are affected by the samples post-processing (i.e., annealing) as well as by heating. Therefore, the low magnetic field region of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of as-prepared sample at ambient temperature and at $T = 300$ °C is rather different. In contrast, the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies at low magnetic field region of the stress-annealed microwires ($T_{ann} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa) are rather similar.

4. Conclusion

We observed substantial changes in GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, value, and magnetic field dependence and in the hysteresis loops upon heating of $\text{Co}_{69.2}\text{Fe}_{3.6}\text{Ni}_{1.5}\text{B}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{1.5}\text{C}_{1.2}$ glass-coated microwires with nearly-zero magnetostriction coefficient. The changes in hysteresis loop shape upon heating correlate with the modification of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies. In as-prepared sample and the sample subjected to Joule heating the hysteresis loop transformation from linear to rectangular upon heating correlates with the change in $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies from double-peak to single-peak. However, after stress-annealing the hysteresis loops and $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies are less affected by the heating. Therefore, stress-annealed microwires can be more suitable for the development of magnetic sensors working at extended temperature ranges. In microwire stress-annealed at 300 °C for 118 MPa, the $\Delta Z/Z_m$ -magnitude is almost constant within the whole range of studied temperature. On the other hand, higher sensitivity of GMI effect upon heating is observed in as-prepared and Joule heated microwires. The origin of observed temperature dependencies is discussed considering contributions of the relaxation and the temperature dependence of the internal stresses, the Hopkinson effect, the induced magnetic anisotropy, and the dependence of the magnetostriction coefficient on temperature.

5. Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Corte-Leon: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **I. Skorvanek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **F. Andrejka:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **M. Jakubcin:** Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **V. Zhukova:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **A. Zhukov:**

Fig. 12. Low field region of $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at ambient temperature in as-prepared (a) and stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{amb} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa (b) and measured at 300 in as-prepared (c) and stress-annealed for 1 h at $T_{amb} = 300$ °C for $\sigma = 118$ MPa (d).

Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors of the manuscript “Exploring the Temperature Dependence of Magnetic Properties and Magnetoimpedance Effect in Co-rich Microwires” by P. Corte-Leon, I. Skorvanek, F. Andrejka, M. Jakubcin, V. Zhukova and A. Zhukov (previous ref. JSAMD-D-23-00279) declare no competing financial or/and non-financial interests.

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